

King Shepseskaf and his Pyramid, the Mastabat Fara'un

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Recently, in arXiv, we have proposed a discussion about the Egyptian kings Shepseskaf and Userkaf, in relation to an eclipse of 2471 BC, a total eclipse that was visible from the Delta of the Nile. Here we must focus on some further points, specifically on two, which we have not previously discussed in arXiv:2412.20407, but that we can find reported by Italian newspapers and websites, particularly Wired Italia. One of these two points is regarding the end of the dominance of the solar cult, as declared by archaeoastronomer G. Magli, in newspapers and websites. This end would have been caused by the above-mentioned solar eclipse, which Shepseskaf would have witnessed and reacted accordingly. We will stress that the solar cult did not end with the end of the Fourth Dynasty; it became dominant during the following Fifth Dynasty. The kings of this V Dynasty, besides pyramids, built solar temples too. Regarding the news, we must also consider what is reported by earth.com, where we find it said that "evidence of this eclipse exists ... in... ancient texts". No ancient Egyptian text refers to the eclipse of 2471 BC. The other point we discuss is the interior of Shepseskaf's mastaba. We will see that the orientations of the entrance of the Mastabat Fara'un and of its burial chamber are the same as in the case of the Giza pyramids. Therefore, in the last part of our work, we prefer to add also a discussion about the orientation of entrances, burial chambers and sarcophagi of the pyramids of the Fourth Dynasty, including Seila, Meidum, Bent, Red and Giza pyramids. It is strictly necessary to note that the Mastabat Fara'un was restored by Khaemwaset, the fourth son of Ramesses II. We know this fact from an inscription on the monument. In this inscription, we can find that the Shepseskaf's burial place was defined as a pyramid.

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In arXiv, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.20407>, we have proposed a discussion about the Egyptian kings Shepseskaf and Userkaf, of the IV and V Dynasty respectively, in relation to the eclipse of 2471 BC, a total eclipse visible from the Delta of the Nile, eclipse which has been the subject of 2024 Giulio Magli's arXiv/2412.13640. Besides the problems addressed in my arXiv/2412.20407, mainly regarding the chronology, here we must focus on some further points, particularly on two of them that we have not mentioned before. Since we can find them reported by Italian newspapers and websites, particularly by Wired Italia, it is necessary to further write some notes. One of the two points is regarding the end of the dominance of the solar cult, as told by archaeoastronomer G. Magli to the press; this end would have been caused by the solar eclipse, which Shepseskaf would have witnessed, reacting accordingly. We will stress that the solar cult does not end with the end of the Fourth Dynasty but becomes dominant during the following Fifth Dynasty. The V Dynasty is characterized by the building of pyramids and sun temples.

The other point is the interior of Shepseskaf's mastaba. We will show that the orientations of the entrance of the monument and of the burial chamber are the same as in the case of the Giza pyramids. It is strictly necessary to note that this mastaba was restored by Khaemwaset, the fourth son of Ramesses II. We know this fact by an inscription on the mastaba. Due to the interest of Khaemwaset for the monuments of the Old Kingdom, this son of Ramesses II is considered the first 'Egyptologist' of history. In the Khaemwaset inscription, we can find that the Shepseskaf's burial place was defined as a pyramid.

About the eclipse of 2471 BC, we also consider what is reported by earth.com, where we find it said that "evidence of this eclipse exists ... in... ancient texts". No ancient Egyptian text refers to the eclipse of 2471 BC.

As previously told, Khaemwaset's inscription defines the Shepseskaf's mastaba as a "pyramid". We can see also the hieroglyph of the "pyramid" on a "fragment of limestone relief from the tomb of Shepseskaf: this slab bears a single line of text, carved in fair sunk relief, containing the name of the 'Pyramid' of King Shepseskaf - the 'Mastabat Fara'un'." at the British Museum, object EA1234

https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA1234

It is evident that when a newspaper or a website is reporting news regarding research, the usual short lengths of their articles are necessarily compressing them into a few elements. Therefore, it is also clear that these elements, and an absence of cross-examination, turn the research into a few features the readers can appreciate. In this framework, we move to comment on the two points mentioned above.

On January 22, 2025, the Milan newspaper, [Il Giorno](#), published an article entitled "*The solar eclipse and a divine omen behind the end of the Egyptian pyramids: the thesis of the archaeoastronomer Magli of the Politecnico di Milano*", subtitled "*According to the theory put forward by the professor, the pharaoh Shepseskaf in 2471 BC would have interpreted the astronomical phenomenon as a 'curse'. This is how it revolutionized the following route of ancient history.*"

Note that the newspaper is asserting that the eclipse changed the Egyptian history.

According to Magli, arXiv 2024, arxiv.org/abs/2412.13640, Shepseskaf was the last pharaoh of the Fourth Dynasty of the Old Kingdom of Egypt. Contrary to what was said by Il Giorno, the construction of the Egyptian pyramids continued even after the end of the Fourth Dynasty, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Egyptian_pyramids, and therefore the title of the article, saying "*The solar eclipse is a divine omen behind the end of the Egyptian pyramids*", is misleading. The subtitle is also mentioning a 'curse', that of the Gods against the king, and, as previously told, of a 'revolution' of Egyptian history. No ancient document supports such a 'revolution'.

I have already discussed Magli's article in detail in my arXiv, regarding particularly the chronology related to the Fourth Dynasty. Let us just remember that the Fourth Dynasty begins with Snefru. The second pharaoh is Cheops, the one of the Great Pyramid of Giza. Then follow Djedefre, Khafre, Bicheris, Menkaure, Shepseskaf and (perhaps) Djedefptah. The first pharaoh of the Fifth Dynasty was Userkaf, who had a pyramid built for himself, not a cube or a cone or a cylinder, but a pyramid.

However, what is the "end" of a dynasty? What does it mean? "The division of ancient Egyptian kings into dynasties is an invention of Manetho's Aegyptiaca, intended to adhere more closely to the expectations of Manetho's patrons, the Greek rulers of Ptolemaic Egypt." (Wikipedia, Redford, 2001, [wikipedia.org/wiki/Shepseskaf#End_of_dynasty](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shepseskaf#End_of_dynasty)). "In modern Egyptology no sharp division is understood to have taken place between the fourth and fifth dynasties" (Wikipedia, Bárta, 2016).

We will see in our discussion, when we will mention Ramesses II, that the concept of ‘Dynasty’ was far from the Egyptian mind. To Ramesses II, all the kings that ruled before him are of his ‘Dynasty’, that is, the kingship in Egypt was one and only one. It started with the Old Kingdom and arrived at Ramesses II.

There is no chronology which is precise enough to establish that the eclipse of 2471 BC occurred during the reign of Shepseskaf. Please consider the reading of note 1 in Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shepseskaf>. “Proposed dates for the reign of Shepseskaf: 2523–2519 BC,[2][3][4][5] ending 2510 BC,[6] 2511–2506 BC,[7][8] 2504–2500BC,[9] 2503–2498 BC,[10][11][12] ending 2494 BC,[13][14] 2486–2479 BC,[15] 2472–2467 BC,[16][17][18] ending 2465 BC,[19] 2462–2457 BC,[20] 2461–2456 BC,[7] 2442–2436 BC,[21] 2441–2438 BC,[22] 2441–2436 BC,[23] ending 2435 BC,[24] 2396–2392 BC.[25] Radiocarbon studies have yielded the following intervals for Shepseskaf date of accession to the throne: 2538–2498 BC with 68% probability, 2556–2476 BC with 95% probability.[26]”. The numbers in parentheses are the references given by Wikipedia; it is very easy to verify that Wikipedia reports the chronological data as they appear in literature. Here the [link to archived item](#). Ref.26 is Ramsey et al., 2010.

King/queen	Accession dates (B.C.E.)					
	Shaw (18)	Hornung <i>et al.</i> (21)	68%		95%	
			from	to	from	to
Shepseskaf	2503	2441	2538	2498	2556	2476

How can anyone say that Shepseskaf saw the eclipse of 2471 BC for sure?

About chronology, let's see again what the article in *Il Giorno* says. Shepseskaf was the last pharaoh of the Fourth Dynasty, according to Magli, and during his reign, again according to Magli, the total eclipse of 2471 BC took place. “According to Magli ... *The available data and calculations regarding historical eclipses show that on April 1, 2471 BC, a significant and unexpected event occurred on the Nile Delta: a total solar eclipse, with the path of totality almost centered on the sacred city of Buto. ... The darkening of the solar disk could have been interpreted "as a divine omen," Magli explains. "This would have pushed Shepseskaf to break with tradition," triggering "a crisis that led to the end of the dominance of the solar cult in royal architectural choices," this is the thesis supported by Magli.*” ([Il Giorno](#)).

As mentioned above, it is NOT true that the Egyptians stopped building pyramids. If we mean the "big" pyramids, already with Menkaure the dimensions have been reduced. However, a pyramid of the Fifth Dynasty, that of Neferirkare, has a volume which is larger than that of the pyramid of Menkaure. **And it is a pyramid.**

The eclipse of 2471 BC is NOT a 'historic eclipse'. There is NO written text that reports the event. "The oldest eclipse. A tablet found in the ancient city of Ugarit, in modern-day Syria, contains indications of what is probably the oldest recorded solar eclipse. There are two possible dates on which this happened: March 5, 1223 BC or May 3, 1375 BC. The Babylonians are the fathers of Western astronomy: they noted the motion of the stars, the Sun and the planets for astrological

purposes, but it is from them that the study of the motions of the sky reached Egypt, Greece and then through the Romans arrived to us." <https://www.wired.it/gallery/eclissi-solare-totale-storia-leggende-foto/>.

It is also crucial to ask yourself and understand how eclipse dates are determined (see please my previous discussion of about 2471 BC eclipse in arXiv). The idea that an eclipse could affect the governance and religion of ancient Egypt is by Jane B. Sellers, 1992.

What does the Il Giorno article also say?

"Magli studied the Egyptian pyramids in particular, adhering to the dating method proposed in 2000 by Egyptologist Kate Spence, known as the "simultaneous transit method": a theory according to which, calculating the deviation of the pyramid from the current astronomical north, it is presumable [to guess] that an orientation ceremony of the Pyramid of Cheops took place exactly in 2467 BC".

How is this possible? Pay attention to what the article in Il Giorno says. The article tells us that:

- 1) the eclipse occurred in 2471 BC, during the reign of Shepseskaf, the last pharaoh of the Fourth Dynasty;
- 2) the orientation ceremony of the pyramid of Cheops "took place exactly in 2467 BC".

Cheops is the second pharaoh of the Fourth Dynasty. How is it possible that the ceremony relating to his pyramid (2467 BC) took place AFTER the eclipse (2471 BC) during the reign of the last pharaoh of the same dynasty? ***How is it possible that Il Giorno reports such an enormous contradiction? And let us note that it is told "exactly in 2467 BC".***

Regarding Khufu's pyramid: "Without a doubt, the Great Pyramid was commissioned by the Old Kingdom pharaoh Khufu (Cheops). The British Museum and Cairo's Egyptian Museum give his regnal dates as 2589 to 2566 BCE. Egyptologists Mark Lehner, who has conducted fieldwork at Giza for four decades, and Zahi Hawass, a former Egyptian government official in charge of Giza, argued for the later range of 2509 to 2483 BCE in their massive 2017 book, *Giza and the Pyramids*" (Robinson, 2022).

From the article in [Il Giorno](#): *"The darkening of the solar disk could have been interpreted "as a divine omen", explains Magli. "This would have pushed Shepseskaf to break with tradition", triggering "a crisis that led to **the end of the dominance of the solar cult in royal architectural choices**", is the thesis supported by Magli".* Please read the discussion in *The pyramids*, by Miroslav Verner, 2014, on the mastaba of Shepseskaf. www.google.it/books/, and in Wikipedia too https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shepseskaf#Decision_to_build_a_mastaba

The burden of proof to show that the eclipse of 2471 BC occurred during the reign of Shepseskaf is with Magli. *Onus probandi incumbit ei qui dicit, non ei qui negat.* It must be Magli who proves it, not others to disprove it. As we have seen in Note 1 of Wikipedia, we start from 2523–2519 BC and go up to 2396–2392 BC. The reign of Shepseskaf from 2472 to 2467 BC is in Mark Lehner, 1997.

Here in the following Table, the chronology is given as we can find it in the Lehner's book of 1997.

Old Kingdom	BC
4 th dynasty	2575-2465
Snefru	2575-2551
Khufu	2551-2528

Djedefre	2528-2520
Khafre	2520-2494
Menkaure	2490-2472
Shepseskaf	2472-2467

BUT we know that “Egyptologists Mark Lehner, who has conducted fieldwork at Giza for four decades, and Zahi Hawass, a former Egyptian government official in charge of Giza, argued for [regnal dates of Khufu] the later range of 2509 to 2483 BCE in their massive 2017 book, *Giza and the Pyramids*” (Robinson, 2022). Then, the regnal dates of Shepseskaf must be later too. Keep in mind that there are at least 50 years between the reign of Khufu and that of Shepseskaf. We are about 2430 BC. And the eclipse? during the reign of Khafre.

It has been said that Magli has the same chronology as Lehner, 1997, but that Lehner exposed a new chronology in 2017. Some might say that Magli has never followed Lehner. Here is a screenshot of a [book](#) by Magli, *Architecture, Astronomy and Sacred Landscape in Ancient Egypt*, 2013. Search for "Shepsekaf".

There is no reference to Lehner, but Lehner's text is earlier (1997) than Magli's. The years are the same.

Let's not limit ourselves to *Il Giorno*. Let's move on to an article published on February 1, 2025, website [mondointasca](#). The article, [mondointasca](#), concludes that "Professor Magli's study links a specific astronomical event to a paradigm shift in funerary architecture for the first time, while also providing a new chronological anchor for the reign of Shepseskaf."

Does Magli provide a new chronological 'anchor'? The eclipse? The eclipse as a chronological anchor only works in the Lehner scheme, 1997, but Lehner changed the chronology in 2017. And note also that there are many other Egyptian chronological schemes.

Previously, I said that the idea that an eclipse could affect the government and religion of ancient Egypt is by Jane B. Sellers, 1992. Sellers linked the eclipse of 2471 BC to the reign of Userkaf, the first king of the Fifth Dynasty. She talks about Pe, which is the Egyptian name for Buto (the city of Pe in Greek). Sellers' approach has not been welcomed by Egyptologists indeed (see <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.20407>). In *mondointasca*, it is referred specifically to the “funerary architecture”. This architecture is closely linked to the social and religious conditioning of the period. The article introduces the concept of "paradigm shift". This “paradigm shift” is that Shepseskaf had a mastaba built for himself as a tomb instead of a pyramid. The next king, Userkaf, made again a “paradigm shift” because he returned to the pyramid. That is, the “paradigm shift” only worked for

Shepseskaf (see please my further discussion of the Mastabat Fara'un). Let us remember Il Giorno; was this “paradigm shift” that “revolutionized the following route of ancient history”?

Shepseskaf, before putting his hand to his tomb, had to finish the pyramid of Menkaure. He did not have the workers and logistics to have a pyramid made, since they were busy at the pyramid of Menkaure, and so he opted for a simpler building, although being a huge monument.

In Magli's [arXiv, 2024](#), we find told that “All in all, the unprecedented and unequalled shape of the Shepseskaf tomb is really a mystery. A number of proposed solutions for this mystery is available, most of them being *frankly* very weak, or even untenable.” “Frankly very weak”, according to Magli. No reference given to other opinions. Magli continues: “For instance, it has been proposed that it was a temporary backup for his own tomb while the king was finishing Menkaure's complex (Verner 2002) – but this *blatantly conflicts with the raffinate interiors*.” The reported sentence is telling that, according to Magli, the position of Verner is untenable because the interior of the tomb is raffinate. Magli is also telling in the same [arXiv](#), “As far as the interior is concerned, I was granted several years ago by the Egyptian authorities (former SCA) of the permission of visiting it (the whole area is closed to the public) and I can testify that it is really a IV dynasty royal monument also inside” (Magli, 2024). We will return at the mastaba.

To see the interior, and how *raffinate* is it, please visit <https://laciviltaegizia.org/2021/02/02/la-mastabat-el-faraun/>, [archived](#) , <https://www.meretsegerbooks.com/gallery/451/shepseskaf-mastaba-faraun> , https://isida-project.ucoz.com/egypt_mar_2013/saqqara_shepseskaf.htm , [archived](#). This last web site writes: “The interiors of the Mastaba resemble the internal structure of the pyramids, in particular the Userkaf pyramid in Saqqara.” And, “The internal structures of Shepseskaf Mastaba have granite masonry. In this connection there is another parallel - with ancient buildings. The internal rooms of Mastaba were made with the same technique and the same material as the Granite Temple in Giza.”

Given the example of Menkaure who had died before the pyramid was finished, Shepseskaf opted for a faster worksite, in a place very close to a stone quarry, near the pyramid of Snefru. This is what Verner says, 2014. It should also be noted that it was Mark Lehner who first defined the Shepseskaf mastaba in the style of the Buto shrines (“With an outer slope of 70°, it may have risen in two steps and certainly took the form of a Buto shrine - a vaulted top between vertical ends”, Lehner, 1997).

Wired Italia, <https://web.archive.org/web/20250128133928/https://www.wired.it/article/grandi-piramidi-egitto-fine-causa-eclissi/>, by Sara Carmignani.

“**The data and calculations available on historical eclipses** show that on April 1, 2471 BC, a total solar eclipse occurred, with the totality band almost centered on the sacred city of Buto. The Giza area and the capital, Memphis, were also very close to the totality zone. “The total eclipse of 2471 BC could have been interpreted as a divine omen - comments Magli - This would have prompted Shepseskaf to break with tradition, reflecting a crucial symbolic and political change. **The eclipse therefore seems to have triggered a crisis that led to the end of the dominance of the solar cult in royal architectural choices**” ”. To this statement by Magli, reported by Sara Carmignani, it immediately follows the conclusion of her article: “The pyramids continued to be built even after the reign of Shepseskaf, but no one as the Giza monuments. According to what was reconstructed in a Livescience news, the last known royal pyramid was the one built for Pharaoh Ahmose I, who reigned until about 1525 BC.” Livescience article is by Owen Jarus.

We have already said that the eclipse of 2471 BC is not a historical eclipse. There are no contemporary texts that report the event. “End of the dominance of the solar cult in royal architectural choices”?

The Fifth Dynasty is characterized by solar temples! Pyramids and solar temples, what a “ending” indeed! Please consider the following list:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Egyptian_sun_temple

- *Nekhenre* (Nekhen-Ra), "The fortress of Re", built by [Userkaf](#)
- *Sekhetre*, "The field of Re", built by [Sahure](#)
- *Setibre*, "The favourite place of Re", built by [Neferirkare Kakai](#)
- *Hetepre*, "The offering place of Re", built by [Neferefre](#)
- Conjectural: *Hotepibre*, "Satisfied is the heart of Re", started by [Shepseskare](#)
- *Shesepibre* "Joy of the heart of Re", built by [Nyuserre Ini](#)
- *Akhetre*, "The horizon of Re", built by [Menkauhor Kaiu](#).

This is the reason why Jane Sellers placed the eclipse in the time of Userkaf's reign: the sun wins over darkness.

How is it possible that Wired Italia publishes that, with Shepseskaf, the dominance of the solar cult ended if the next dynasty was characterized by solar temples? The first king of the V Dynasty, Userkaf. "His reign heralded the ascendancy of the cult of Ra, who effectively became Egypt's state god during the Fifth Dynasty. Userkaf may have been a high-priest of Ra before ascending the throne, and built a sun temple, known as the Nekhenre, between Abusir and Abu Gurab. In doing so, he instituted a tradition followed by his successors over a period of 80 years." <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Userkaf>

Again, from the **Wired Italia** article. "But what is the explanation for this break with previous traditions? Over time, **several hypotheses have been formulated, such as the fact that the rectangular monument was a temporary construction** built by the pharaoh while waiting for another funerary complex to be raised, perhaps in the shape of a pyramid. **Magli, however, believes that the care with which the interior of Shepseskaf's tomb were built does not exactly agree with this hypothesis.** According to the professor, a **more plausible hypothesis** could concern an astronomical event that occurred with **good probability** during the reign of Shepseskaf."

"Plausible" and "good probability" are terms that are good for Wired Italia of course, not for a physicist. How had the probability been determined, and what this probability was? Wired Italia had to ask Magli about.

Magli says that the mastaba of Shepseskaf was not a temporary construction because it is well finished inside. See once more the interior of the Mastabat Fara'un at the web page https://isida-project.ucoz.com/egypt_mar_2013/saqqara_shepseskaf.htm , [archived](#). See please my further specific discussion about the interior of the monument.

Wikipedia: "Remnants of a decorated dark basalt sarcophagus were uncovered there although the burial chamber was never finished and, in all probability, never used.[41]". Wikipedia gives Ref.41 as Tyldesley, Joyce (2005). À la découverte des pyramides d'Égypte. Champollion (in French). I have not yet verified this reference.

The inner chambers, with the massive sarcophagus, corridors and passageways, had been built before the mastaba envelope was completed. Thus, it is possible that the core of the building was designed to be the final burial environment of the king. The outer shell was the part that could be modified into a pyramid.

Pyramid?

We must refer to an article by Lloyd, 2024. In the Past, <https://the-past.com/feature/the-first-egyptologists/>, entitled “The First Egyptologists. Alan Lloyd considers the motives of certain individuals from antiquity for studying ancient Egypt. Were they Egyptologists?”.

“Without doubt, the best-known ancient Egyptian ‘Egyptologist’ is Khaemwaset, the fourth son of Ramesses II. He enjoyed a brilliant career across the entire spectrum of activities expected of a royal prince, but is particularly renowned for his religious and architectural activities. We are fortunate in having a number of inscriptions that give an insight into his motivation for working on ancient monuments, and of these texts I [Lloyd] want to examine two: the inscription on the Mastabat Fara’un constructed for the Fourth Dynasty king Shepseskaf (c.2503-2498 BC) at Saqqara South, and the text recording Khaemwaset’s work on the statue of Kawab, eldest son of Khufu, now in the Cairo Museum.” (Lloyd, 2024).

The inscription in the Shepseskaf mastaba tells to us: “His Majesty instructed the Chief Controller of Craftsmen [i.e. High Priest of Ptah], Sem-Priest, King’s Son, Khaemwaset to establish the name of the King of Upper and Lower Egypt Shepseskaf [i.e. on the monument], since his name could not be found on his pyramid, inasmuch as the Sem-Priest Khaemwaset loved to restore the monuments of the Kings of Upper and Lower Egypt, because of what they had achieved, making firm again what had fallen into ruin. By [the Sem-Priest, King’s Son, Khaemwaset]” (Lloyd, 2024).

Look at the inscription, so you can see that there is the symbol of the pyramid.

https://i0.wp.com/the-past.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/post-1_image2-14.jpg?w=1230&ssl=1

For Khaemwaset it was a pyramid. And Khaemwaset was an Egyptologist.

Khaemwaset is acting at Mastabat Fara’un “on his father’s command”. Lloyd also notes that the inscription is related to the “concerns over legitimacy, which was of particular importance to this family because their right to the throne of Egypt was far from obvious. This preoccupation is particularly evident in the cenotaph of Sety I at Abydos. There we find a spectacular king-list depicting Sety making offerings to a long sequence of kings beginning with the First Dynasty, and running right down to the Nineteenth, a list that carefully avoids mentioning any ruler (such as Akhenaten) who might be regarded as illegitimate” (Lloyd, 2024). Therefore, it was not a problem of ‘Dynasty’, but a problem of legitimacy.

For what is regarding Ramesses’ Dynasty, “It was possible to assert [its] legitimacy by showing concern for the monuments of predecessors, and this is where Khaemwaset became highly relevant as the agent of Ramesses’ strategy. It explains why the cartouches of Shepseskaf and Ramesses are linked at the beginning of the inscription, and why Ramesses appears at the very beginning of the main text. However, the text also insists that Khaemwaset himself had a particular interest in restoring ancient monuments, motivated, at least in part, by his admiration for the achievements of earlier kings, themes which we shall find recurring later” (Lloyd, 2024).

“The text unequivocally asserts that Sety – and ipso facto the dynasty – is the legitimate **successor to a long line of Egyptian kings running back to the beginning of Egyptian history**. His son Ramesses shared this concern, as is made clear by his close self-identification with the great Eighteenth Dynasty Pharaoh Amenhotep III. This extended to usurping the latter’s monuments on a grand scale and becoming, in a very important sense, Amenhotep himself” (Lloyd, 2024).

Magli saw the well finished interior. Let us stress that the original interior did not mention the name of its owner. This name has been written by Khaemwaset. It is possible that Khaemwaset restored the interior, to consolidate the building. As the reader can find in the following discussion, the floor of the burial chamber had been removed in antiquity.

“While the conservation of a site is a comparatively new feature of modern archaeology, it is by no means to be regarded as a modern innovation. Prince Khaemwaset, the fourth son of Ramesses II, visited the pyramids at Giza and Saqqara and, noting the neglect of the pyramids and temples, resolved to do something about it. At Saqqara the Step Pyramid of Djoser, the tomb of Shepseskaf, and the lesser pyramid of Unas all benefited from his attentions as did the Pyramid of Sahure and a Sun Temple of Neuserre. Inscriptions left on these monuments outline Khaemwaset's 'desire to restore the monuments of the Kings of Upper and Lower Egypt because of what they had done, the strength of which (monuments) was falling into decay'.” (Callaghan, 1991, mentioning Kitchen, 1982).

A further example!

“Solar eclipse **may have changed the architecture of ancient Egypt forever**”. [02-05-2025. Jordan Joseph](#). NO, it is not true. No. After the Shepseskaf mastaba, of the IV Dynasty we have only the Pyramid of Khentkaus I. This pyramid – actually, it is a mastaba - is located in Giza and is sometimes referred to as the "fourth pyramid." It was built for Queen Mother Khentkaus I. She ruled between the Fourth and the Fifth Dynasty. The kings of the V Dynasty used pyramids, not mastabas.

“This concept was explored by archaeoastronomer Giulio Magli from the Polytechnic University of Milan. His ideas connect a rare celestial occurrence with a change in Old Kingdom traditions that **altered pharaonic structures forever**.” This sentence means nothing. It is necessary to explain in what manner the structures had been altered.

Shepseskaf “chose a design for his tomb that contrasted sharply with the pyramids of his predecessors. This marked a big change in how Egypt’s rulers showcased their legacies.” NO, see the following discussion.

“ “Shepseskaf made revolutionary choices for his funerary monument, which seem to be an explicit rejection of the solar tradition established by his predecessors,” explained Magli, an Italian astrophysicist and archaeo-astronomer.” Why revolutionary? Why? No explanation.

Jordan Joseph writes: “Significance of the eclipse in Egypt. **Evidence of this eclipse** exists in astronomical simulations and ancient texts that hint at unusual solar behavior. The Old Kingdom’s architectural choices may have reflected a **deeper anxiety** about the cosmic order.” NO, this eclipse is not a historical eclipse. NO document exists, NO Egyptian inscription is describing this eclipse!

What? Deeper anxiety? Deeper of what?

“The differences in his [Shepseskaf] tomb’s style are more apparent when compared with the strict solar alignment favored by earlier rulers.” NO, the Shepseskaf mastaba is oriented as the pyramids! The axis of the monument is north-south exactly as that of the pyramids. The burial chamber is east – west as the burial chambers in the Giza Pyramids. See the following discussion.

“Permanent shift from solar traditions”. PERMANENT SHIFT?!?! The V Dynasty is characterized by solar temples!

Shepseskaf and Mastabat Fara'un

The assumption that the Shepseskaf's tomb is like a shrine to Buto is not accepted by everyone. Consider the following literature excerpts carefully.

“King Shepseskaf ... The Turin Canon allows him four years. In this time he would have had to complete his father's funerary temples and construct for himself the so-called Mastabat Fara'un, half-way between Saqqara and Dahshur. The form of this tomb differs from the pyramids of the other kings of the Fourth Dynasty. It was a rectangular mastaba construction with a rounded top and vertical end-pieces which gave it the form of the **usual stone sarcophagus**. Inside, the burial apartments were lined with granites. **The heavy masonry and sound workmanship betoken work in the best Fourth Dynasty traditions**. Nearly all the masonry of the temple has been plundered. The niched outer court and vaulted causeway were hastily finished in brick, probably after the death of the king. The monument was identified by a statue fragment bearing a broken cartouche.” (Cambridge Ancient History).

“The building is a large mastaba of the **usual shape**; it was evidently once cased with fine limestone, which, as usual, has vanished, leaving rough stepped courses to view. Access may be had to the interior passages and chambers. ‘A sloping passage turns horizontal at the bottom, passes three slides for portcullises, and lastly opens into a **chamber running east and west**, with a ridge-roof. From the west end opens another chamber with a barrel-roof. And from the east end of the south side is a short horizontal passage, with four recesses and a small chamber. **The arrangement is closely like that of a pyramid**, and every part is equalled in that of Unas at Saqqara, though rather different arranged’ (Petrie, History of Egypt, I, p.94). The mastaba had a funerary temple on its east side” (Baikie, 2018).

“The entrance to the subterranean system of chambers is located on the shorter, northern side. A passage with a slope of 23°30' leads down into the ground. It was originally 20.75 metres long, but due to a collapse it is now only 16.3 metres long.” [Wikipedia](#).

“The mastaba and close-up views of the inner chambers of Shepseskaf”, Date 17 July 2013, 00:13:36. Author R.F.Morgan. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Shepseskaf_Iso.jpg

Let us stress that the orientation of Mastabat Fara'un is the same as the pyramids of the Old Kingdom.

Mastabat Fara'un Courtesy Google Earth.

Menkaure's pyramid Courtesy Google Earth

“The fact that Shepseskaf chose to build a mastaba rather than a pyramid has puzzled scholars. There are multiple theories about why he would have done this. The most accepted theory is that he was planning to build a pyramid. However, he died soon after the work of his tomb commenced. Therefore, either his successor or his queen might have converted the tomb into a mastaba so that he could be entombed there. This is something that even the Palermo Stone, one of the oldest surviving texts of the Old Kingdom, hints at.” (Romney, 2021).

“On the Palermo Stone, for the first year of the Shepseskaf, the last pharaoh of the Fourth Dynasty, we are told of the selection of a place for his mastaba tomb, to be called “Shelter of Shepseskaf” ” (Dillery, 2015). “The Palermo Stone tells us that in this king’s first year two religious festival were held. It also states that he selected the site for his pyramid at this time and entitled that future pyramid “The Place of Refreshment” ” (Lepre, 1990).

“The floor of the tomb chamber of Shepseskaf’s Mastabat Fara’un was removed in antiquity” (Dodson, 2013).

“At Mastabat el-Fara’un, in the desert south of the tomb of Shepseskaf, there were traces of two transport roads, each 1000 meters long. They approached the site from different locations, probably quarries for local limestone such as was used for the gigantic core blocks of the tomb.” (Arnold, 1991).

Let us consider also, the Mountains of the Pharaohs, 2006, by Zahi Hawass.

“Shepseskaf ruled for only about four years and built a large mastaba, a low rectangular tomb, rather than a pyramid. The last ruler of the 4th Dynasty, a queen named Khentkawes (c. 2519-2513 B.C.), returned to Giza to build a massive tomb, but this was the last great monument built here. Afterward, the site was abandoned in favor of other pyramid fields to the south, although its royal cults continued to flourish for hundreds of years. Giza was the heart of Egypt for three generations.” (Hawass, 2006).

“Shepseskaf ... chose as the site of his own mortuary monument Saqqara, where Djoser had long ago built his Step Pyramid. Instead of a pyramid, Shepseskaf built a huge mastaba of stone, one hundred meters (328 feet) long, seventy-two meters (236 feet) wide, and eighteen meters (fifty-nine feet) high, with a causeway and temple in mud brick. The mastaba **is in the form of a giant sarcophagus**, with rectangular sides and an arched roof. Like the pyramids of his forebears, Shepseskaf's mastaba represents the primeval mound on which the creator god stood to bring the cosmos into being. However, his tomb does not carry the blatantly solar overtones of the true pyramids, and scholars have questioned his relationship to the cult of the sun god ... It may be simply that he did not have the wealth needed to build a pyramid. He seems to have continued with the political systems of his father and in most ways continued the traditions of his 4th Dynasty predecessors. In addition to finishing his father's complex, he honored Menkaure's cult by exempting the priests of the temples from paying taxes. In other ways, Shepseskaf did break with ancient tradition. He married his daughter to a man, Shepsesptah, who was not of royal blood but lived at the palace of Menkaure. This was the first time in pharaonic history that we know of a royal princess marrying a commoner.” (Hawass, 2006).

Queen Khentkawes and the ‘Fourth Pyramid’ at Giza

The ‘fourth pyramid’ at Giza, Courtesy Google Earth.

“ ... Khentkawes, a mysterious female monarch who declared in her own colossal monument at Giza that she was the mother of either one or two kings of Upper and Lower Egypt? Her titles may imply that she ruled Egypt as king in her own right at the end of the Giza dynasty, so it is to this elusive queen that we next turn our attention. A massive monument, in the shape of a giant square sarcophagus on a high podium like that of Shepseskaf, still stands at the south of the Giza plateau between the causeways of Khafre and Menkaure. The base of the tomb, which was cut into the solid rock and cased with fine white limestone, measures forty-five meters (148 feet), and its original height was forty-five meters (148 feet). The size and square base of this tomb prompted its main excavator, Selim Hassan, to christen it the "fourth Giza pyramid." Under the tomb is a burial chamber lined with granite and containing a false door, along with seven small rooms designed to house furniture to be used in the afterlife. A small mortuary temple stands against the eastern face of this structure, and a causeway leads to a valley temple.” (Hawass, 2006).

“The mortuary temple was cased with granite and decorated with religious scenes. On the south- west side of the tomb, Hassan found a boat pit cut into the rock; matching this to the northeast is a rectangular pool entered by eleven steps. This tomb is dedicated to a queen named Khentkawes, who was a daughter of the god and also claimed a title that can be read as either "king's mother and king of Upper and Lower Egypt" or "mother of two kings of Upper and Lower Egypt." Thus, she may have been a ruling queen, the last monarch of the 4th Dynasty. She was certainly a princess; although her parentage is technically unknown, it is most likely that she was the daughter of Menkaure and the sister and wife of Shepseskaf, giving her multiple claims to the throne in the absence of a strong male heir.” (Hawass, 2006).

“As a woman, Khentkawes would not technically have had the right to hold the throne of Egypt, and, not surprisingly, her name does not appear in any of the later king lists. However, her clearly royal monument and her title suggest strongly that however ephemerally, she sat on the throne of the Two Lands. One image of the queen in her tomb, recently examined by Czech Egyptologist Miroslav Verner, shows her wearing a uraeus cobra on her brow, normally seen only on kings during this period. Within her valley temple, a small pyramid city thrived, demonstrating that her cult was active for a significant period of time and providing further evidence that she was accepted as a ruler of Egypt.” (Hawass, 2006).

In Fact, in the [Abydos King List](#), the queen Khentkawes (or Khentkaus I) is not present.

At the beginning of our discussion, we have mentioned king Djedefptah (Thamphthis). “Winfried Seipel and Hermann Alexander Schlögl instead postulate that the historical figure behind Thamphthis could have been queen Khentkaus I.[6] This theory is supported by Khentkaus being depicted in her mortuary temple as a ruling pharaoh with nemes-headress, king's beard and uraeus-diadem on her forehead. But this theory is problematic since Khentkaus' name never appears inside a serekh or royal cartouche.[7]” ([Wikipedia](#), mentioning [6] Seipel, 1980, and [7] Schlögl, 2006).

Userkaf

“Some scholars believe that Khentkawes was the mother of Userkaf, first ruler of the 5th Dynasty, and thus provides a link between the end of the 4th Dynasty and the beginning of the 5th. It has also been theorized that Khentkawes married a priest of Heliopolis and that her children and the heirs to the throne were only half royal.” (Hawass, 2006).

“Userkaf moved the royal court to the site of Abusir, where he built a relatively small pyramid complex. The pyramids of the 5th Dynasty kings were smaller in size than their 4th Dynasty precursors but were more impressive in terms of the areas covered by beautiful relief decoration. In addition to their own mortuary complexes, each king built a sun temple, a monument to Re.” (Hawass, 2006).

“These temples, of which only two have been found and excavated, are nearby and are laid out like the pyramid complexes. The major difference is that, instead of a pyramid, the complexes held monumental obelisks—tapering rectangular shafts that end with a pyramid-shaped top. These sun temples provide strong evidence that the relationship of the royal house to the priesthood of Re had undergone a major shift. The deceased sun god was seen as separate from the deceased king, and thus needed his own mortuary temple.” (Hawass, 2006).

Please note that in the case of Userkaf, between the pyramid and the temple there are 3.5 km. Image Courtesy Google Earth.

Il Giorno again

Let us repeat: “Magli explains. *"This would have pushed Shepseskaf to break with tradition," triggering "a crisis that led to the end of the dominance of the solar cult in royal architectural choices," this is the thesis supported by Magli.*” ([Il Giorno](#)). It seems that the V Dynasty had a dominance of the solar cult. But *il Giorno* does not mention the following Fifth Dynasty, and the pyramids or its kings or the solar temples. No. *Il Giorno* tells us just: “moreover, this tomb was not visible from Heliopolis, the center of the cult of the Sun”. What? What does it mean?

In his arXiv, 2412.13640, Magli wrote: “All in all, the tomb of the king speaks to us – both in its placement not in view from Heliopolis, and in its shape connected to a sacred place in the Delta [Buto]– about a strong break operated by the king with respect to the solar cult”. Lehner wrote that the form of Mastabat Fara’un was that of a Buto-shrine, but Hawass wrote that the tomb is a giant sarcophagus. We will return to Heliopolis in a further section of this work. The Cambridge Ancient History tells us that the shape is that of the usual sarcophagus too.

Magli observes the absence of the Ra particle in the name of Shepseskaf. Magli added that “The almost traumatic relevance that this break must have had can be seen also a posteriori by the complexity of the process of restoration and renewal initiated by his successor: the founder of the fifth dynasty Userkaf.” In the name “Userkaf” too, we do not find the particle Ra. And also in the names of Khufu and Snefru.

Throne names: Shepses kaf , šps-s-k3-f, His ka is noble. <https://pharaoh.se/ancient-egypt/pharaoh/shepseskaf/> - User kaf, wsr-k3-f, His ka is strong. <https://pharaoh.se/ancient-egypt/pharaoh/userkaf/> The web site pharaoh.se is giving the Shepseskaf’s successor as Baufra, <https://pharaoh.se/ancient-egypt/pharaoh/baufra/> Throne name: Ba ef Ra, b3.f-r‘, His soul is that of Ra. The name Baufra is in the Wadi Hammamat inscription (Drioton, 1954).

Wadi Hammamat list

We can find the article by Drioton at gizamedia.rc.fas.harvard.edu. « L'énumération commence par les noms de Chéops, Radjedef et Chéphrên, dont les règnes constituent une séquence historiquement bien établie. Mais elle se poursuit par l'introduction de deux personnages, Hordjedef et Bioufrê, dont on connaissait l'existence, mais sans avoir aucun indice qu'ils eussent jamais été rois. » (Drioton, 1954).

« Quoiqu'il en soit cette apparition de deux noms inattendus, immédiatement après celui de Chéphrên, dans une énumération de souverains de la IV^e Dynastie, évoque les difficultés que les historiens ont rencontrées jusqu'à présent pour établir la liste des derniers rois de cette dynastie. **Le Papyrus de Turin offre une lacune de quatre noms entre Chéphrên et Ouserkaf, le fondateur de la V^e Dynastie.** Une fois restitués Mycérimus et Chepseskaf, il reste encore deux noms à y placer. La liste d'Abydos, qui n'est qu'un abrégé, porte simplement pour cette époque la séquence : Chéphrên, Mycérimus, Chepseskaf. La liste de Sakkarah est mutilée à cet endroit et elle ne saurait être d'aucune utilité. En ce qui concerne les listes grecques, Manéthon donne pour la fin de la IV^e Dynastie: Souphis, Menkérès, Rhatoisès, Bikhéris, Seberkérès et Tamphthys ; Eratosthène énumère : Raouôsis, Biourès, Saôphis I, Saôphis II et Moskhérès » (Drioton, 1954).

From the IV to the V Dynasty

“Texts in several tombs at Giza indicate that there was no dramatic political break between the 4th and 5th Dynasties. One of Khafre's sons, Sekhemkare, recorded in his tomb that kings Khafre, Menkaure, Shepseskaf, Userkaf, and Sahure all paid him honor. ... **We must remember that the whole concept of dynasties is a later construct, that the Egyptians themselves saw their kings in an unbroken line.** However, there must have been some change of family, and the anomalous rule of Queen Khentkawes I provides evidence of difficulties with the succession” (Hawass, 2006).

Orientations of entrance and burial chamber

We have insisted previously on the orientation of the entrance and burial chamber of Mastabat Fara'un.

Let us consider Muhlestein, 2019, and Table 1. Before showing the Table, let us report (Owen Jarus, 2009): after showing “all four of Snefru's pyramids are like, Muhlestein is able to offer a comparison. He found some interesting parallels between the pyramids. These include - Both Seila and Meidum were built at almost the exact same angle. Meidum is 51 degree, Seila is 52. On the other hand both the Bent and the Red Pyramids have an angle of 43 degrees. - Both Seila and Meidum have causeways that lead nowhere – there is no building at the end of them. - The Red and Bent pyramids have causeways that lead to buildings. - The Bent pyramid and the Red Pyramid have Valley Temples. Meidum and Seila have no evidence of any Valley Temples. - Meidum and the Red Pyramid have mortuary temples. The Seila and Bent the pyramid do not.” (Jarus, 2009). “All four pyramids appear to have altars.” (Jarus, 2009).

Table I, Muhlestein, 2019.

Pyramid	Burial Chamber Orientation	Side of Entrance	Adjacent Structure	Cause-way	Vallet Temple	Altars
Seila	None (uncertain)	None (uncertain)	Porch on East and North	East	No	Two on North, perhaps one on East
Meidum	North-South	North	Eats temple	East	No	One on East
Bent	North-South	North and West	East and North temple	North-East, largely East	Yes	One on East, one on North
Red	East-West	North	East temple	East	Yes	One on East

Meidum: “The burial chamber measures 5.9 by 2.65 metres, which is quite small, yet another sign that the builders were experimenting. There is no sarcophagus and no trace of a burial. Outside the pyramid many elements that would become the standard for pyramid complexes to come were already present as well.” www.ancient-egypt.org/.../snofru/pyramids/meidum-pyramid.html.

Bent Pyramid: “The design of the corridors is similar to the one found in the Great Pyramid of Giza, where the Grand Gallery takes up the place of the ascending corridor. The corridor leads up to the burial chamber (called this despite that it most probably never contained any sarcophagus).” ([Wikipedia](#), mentioning Fakhry, 1961).

“Archaeologists have discovered a large structure to the northeast of the 4,600 year old Bent Pyramid which may be the remains of an ancient harbour. It connects to one of the pyramids temples by way of a 140 meter long causeway.” (Jarus, 2010).

“Although the Red Pyramid is often associated with Pharaoh Sneferu, no direct evidence of his burial or funerary items has been found within it.” www.encounterstravel.com.

Let us add the Giza Pyramids and Mastabat Fara’un

Pyramid	Burial Chamber Orientation	Side of Entrance
Khufu	Chamber East-West Sarcophagus North-South (see this plan)	North
Khafre	Chamber East-West Sarcophagus North-South (see this plan)	North
Menkaure	Antechamber East-West Sarcophagus North-South (see this plan)	North
Shepseskaf	Chamber East-West The sarcophagus is broken	North

Let us continue with the Userkaf pyramid.

Pyramid	Burial Chamber Orientation	Side of Entrance
Userkaf	Chamber East-West The sarcophagus is broken	North

“The pyramid’s entrance is located in the center of its north side and opens onto a substructure that is entirely underground. An 18.5-meter-long descending passage goes down to a horizontal corridor,

that was partially clad with granite blocks and in the middle of which was a huge portcullis slab. Almost immediately behind the portcullis, a short corridor to the east opened on a T-shaped magazine. Further down the main corridor was an antechamber of 4.14 by 3.12 metres. To the west, this antechamber opened onto the actual burial chamber, that measured 7.87 by 3.13 metres (see cut-away of pyramid). The burial chamber was originally completely lined and paved with fine limestone. ... The basalt sarcophagus was found empty”, [5th-dynasty/userkaf/pyramid-complex-at-saqqara/pyramid-of-userkaf.html](https://www.5th-dynasty/userkaf/pyramid-complex-at-saqqara/pyramid-of-userkaf.html) . The offering chapel is to the east of the pyramid.

“The interior of the pyramid of Userkaf at Saqqara begins with an entrance passageway blocked by a granite portcullis which has been broken through. Beyond this a couple of storage rooms - where we enjoyed dodging the bats! - lie off to the left, while ahead there’s an antechamber and then the burial chamber itself. The latter contains only the smashed fragments of a basalt sarcophagus, but it’s an impressive space nonetheless.” (Chris Naunton, [Facebook](#)).

The orientations of the Mastabat Fara’un - entrance, burial chamber - is like those of the Giza Pyramids. The same we find for the Userkaf pyramid.

Let us remember that the first pyramid, the “Djoser's pyramid is made up of six layers and was originally built as a type of rectangular tomb known today as a mastaba (an Arabic word meaning "bench") before being expanded into a step pyramid.” (Jarus, 2023).

Djoser pyramid, Courtesy Google Earth. The default image, on the left, seems to be artistically deforming the pyramid, such as it was falling downside.

Edfu south pyramid, Courtesy Google Earth.

Djoser was the king of the Third Dynasty, the last King was Huni. “The builder and purpose of the [Edfu south] pyramid are unknown. Dreyer and Kaiser thought that it and the other pyramids named above were part of a single building project of Pharaoh Huni, the last ruler of the Third Dynasty. Andrzej Ćwiek mostly agrees, but suggests that Huni's successor, Sneferu (c.2670–2630 BC) the founder of the Fourth Dynasty, was the builder”. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Edfu_South_pyramid

Heliopolis

[Il Giorno](#) wrote about Shepseskaf tomb: “moreover, this tomb was not visible from Heliopolis, the center of the cult of the Sun”. What? What does it mean?

<http://www.ancient-wisdom.com/egyptiheliopolis.htm>

“Heliopolis was once one of the largest cities in ancient Egypt. It was the capital of the cult of Amon-Ra, second only in size by Thebes (Karnak). The chief deity of Heliopolis was the god Atum, who was worshipped in the primary temple, which was known by the names Per-Aat (pr-at; "Great House") and Per-Atum (pr-itmw; "Temple [lit. "House"] of Atum")” (ancient-wisdom).

“Pyramid Alignment Towards Heliopolis: It can be seen that many of the pyramids of the 4th and 5th dynasty were positioned so that their corners aligned towards Heliopolis. It was Hans Goedicke who made the first suggestions over this theory, but they were not published first in a scientific journal, but in a newspaper in 1983 [www.washingtonpost.com]. And what does the theory say? Well, Goedicke noticed that there seems to be a common constructional element at several necropolises: one corner of each structure is often on a straight line with the same corner of other structures in the necropolis. These alignments are found at Giza (south-east corners of Khufu, Khafre and Menkaure), Abusir (north-west-corner of the pyramids of Sahure, Neferirkare und Neferefre), Saqqara (south-east-corners of Sekhemkhet, Djoser, Userkaf und Teti) - and even between necropolises as Goedicke thinks that the east face of Userkaf's Pyramid is aligned with the same face of Khufu's Pyramid several kilometres to the north.” (ancient-wisdom).

“The two larger pyramids, G1 and G2, [Giza 1 and Giza 2], are of almost equal size and are placed in such a way as to have their NE-SW diagonals almost in alignment i.e. not exactly 45° to their meridian but 43° 27'. On maps and aerial photography it also does appear that the southeastern corners of the three pyramids G1, G2 and G3 form a line 45° to the meridian. All this implies, but not proves, that there was perhaps a deliberate intention for this relative positioning of the three pyramids. This has led various Egyptologists, including Hans Goedicke, Mark Lehner and Kate Spence, as well as many archaeo-astronomers including Juan Belmonte and Giulio Magli, to perpetuate a claim that the ancient builders deliberately created a ‘Giza Diagonal’ to symbolically connect the pyramids to the city of Heliopolis” (Bauval, 2013).

“The idea of a symbolic link between the Giza pyramids and Heliopolis, however, is not new. In 1852 the Egyptian-Armenian engineer, Joseph Hekekyan (1807-1875), had published a paper titled ‘Topographical Sketch of Heliopolis and Surrounding Lands’ (the original now in the manuscript archives of the British Library in London), in which Hekekyan noted that the SW-NE diagonal passing through the apex of the Great Pyramid (G1), if extended towards the north-east, will also pass through the apex of the Sesotris I obelisk at Matareya-Heliopolis (a suburb of Cairo) some 24 kilometers away and which, according to Egyptologists, probably marked the location of the Sun Temple of Re at Heliopolis.” (Bauval, 2013). And Bauval continues to describe the works about the ‘diagonal’.

“The theory of the “Giza diagonal” i.e. that the southeast corners of the three pyramids form a diagonal leading to Heliopolis, as well as the theory that G1 and G2 were deliberately designed as one project to represent the sign N27, do not hold to serious scrutiny. Accepting that the layout of the three pyramids was a deliberation based on some plan or ideology, then some other explanation must be sought.” (Bauval, 2013). Of the theory that the pyramids of Khufu and Khafre had been planned by Khufu to create the hieroglyph N27, we have already discussed in <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.20407> . See also Supplementary Materials: “The Egyptian Hieroglyph of the Crested Ibis, from the Cheops' pyramid (Akhet Khufu) to the Akhenaten's Glory of Aten”, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14587114>.

Akhet Khufu is written with the crested ibis! NO N27 sign!

In Nell and Ruggles, 2014, it is told us that: “Jeffreys (1998) and Magli (2009) extend this ‘master plan’ concept, suggesting that a diagonal line running through the south-eastern corners of all three main pyramids (the ‘Giza diagonal’) possibly deliberately pointed directly to the ancient city of Heliopolis (Iunu) some 20km to the north-east, but there are several problems with this hypothesis.13” (Nell & Ruggles, 2014). See please Bauval, 2013, for a complete bibliography. Note 13: “Magli has suggested that the Giza plateau pyramids, as well as several pyramids at Saqqara, Abu Sir, Abu Ghurob, Zawiyet el-Aryan and Abu Roash were all symbolically connected to Heliopolis, home of the sun cult, through the alignments of their corners. However, there are various problems with this idea. For one thing, **the view of Heliopolis from Abu Sir was obstructed: those standing at Abu Sir could not even see the ‘Sun City’** [Heliopolis]. For another, the putative alignment of pyramids at Saqqara involves different corners - the NW corners of Teti’s and Semerkhet’s pyramids, the SE corners of Userkaf’s and Djoser’s pyramids, and a complete diagonal of Unas’ - raising familiar problems of selection” (Nell & Ruggles, 2014).

Abusir – Heliopolis line and elevation profile. There is also to consider effects of Earth curvature and atmosphere refraction. Courtesy Google Earth.

Abu Ghorub – Heliopolis line and elevation profile. Courtesy Google Earth.

Djoser – Userkaf – Heliopolis line and elevation profile. Courtesy Google Earth.

“However, there are various problems with this idea. For one thing, the view of Heliopolis from Abu Sir was obstructed: those standing at Abu Sir could not even see the ‘Sun City’ [Heliopolis]. For another, the putative alignment of pyramids at Saqqara involves different corners - the NW corners of Teti’s and Semerkhet’s pyramids, the SE corners of Userkaf’s and Djoser’s pyramids, and a complete diagonal of Unas’ - raising familiar problems of selection” (Nell & Ruggles, 2014).

Nell and Ruggles please note that, in the case of Userkaf and Djoser pyramids, it is not a problem of selection; like for Abu Sir, the view of Heliopolis is obstructed!

Regarding the Giza pyramids, while the pyramids, which are huge, are clearly visible from Heliopolis, how could ancient people see a specific point of Heliopolis from the Giza plateau in the time of pharaohs? By fire, it is easy according to Magli. But even if it is easy to see fires at a long distance, it does not mean that the ‘diagonal’ was planned to aim to Heliopolis.

Abu Gorab (Abu Gurab, Abu Ghurab)

In [MDPI, 2023](#), Magli wrote: “The idea that the sun temples also should have had a topographical relationship with Heliopolis was explored by several authors ... These studies were based on inter-visibility and pointed out that looking from Heliopolis towards the west bank of the Nile and gazing progressively to the south, an unobstructed line of sight runs to the IVth dynasty pyramid sites of Abu Roash, Giza, and Zawiet el Arian ... When the view moves further south, the visibility is blocked by the rocky outcrop located at the north-west extreme of the plateau ... Abu Gurab, the site of the Sun Temple, **marks the last visible point of the pyramid fields**, those of Abusir, Saqqara, and Dahshur being invisible from Heliopolis.” (Magli, 2023).

What? https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Abu_Gorab Let us repeat once more, with Google Earth, the

elevation profiles, using the same position of Heliopolis and the position of Abu Gurab that Magli used in [MDPI](#).

There are two sun temples, then we propose two maps and two elevation profiles.

Heliopolis as assumed by Magli.

Abu Gorab – Heliopolis line 1 and elevation profile. Courtesy Google Earth.

Abu Gorub – Heliopolis line 2 and elevation profile. Courtesy Google Earth.

Elevation Line 1: from 34 m (Abu Gorab) – 55 m at 11 km – to 19 m (Heliopolis) at 27 km

Elevation Line 2: from 41 m (Abu Gurab) – 54 m at 11 km – to 19 m (Heliopolis) at 27 km

The position of the Cairo Citadel on Line 2; 50 m at 16 km.

The previously given Google Earth profiles tell us that there is some elevation between Heliopolis and the site of the Sun temples. Let us compare with the line connecting the Unfinished Pyramid, Zawiet el Arian and Heliopolis. No elevation is evidenced.

Unfinished Pyramid – Heliopolis line 3 and elevation profile. From Unfinished Pyramid 38 – Nile 15 m 12.5 km – Heliopolis (Magli) 19 m 25.5 km

Let us consider also line 4, from the left 18 m – Nile 16 m 4 km – to right, 49 m 8.7 km. Lines L1 and L2 are at 42-44 meters, at 6 km.

Let us further use the TessaDEM elevation map too.

<https://it-ch.topographic-map.com/map-wlt4nx/Cairo>

Many thanks to the web site for providing such a relevant tool.

Visible or invisible from Heliopolis, or vice versa, note that the two sun temples are not oriented towards Heliopolis. They are oriented to East - West.

TessaDEM map, Courtesy <https://it-it.topographic-map.com>

Khaemwaset again

“Khaemwaset restored the monuments of earlier kings and nobles. Restoration texts were found associated with the pyramid of Unas at Saqqara, the tomb of Shepseskaf called the Mastabat al-Fir’aun, the sun-Temple of Nyuserre Ini, the Pyramid of Sahure, the Pyramid of Djoser, and the Pyramid of Userkaf. Inscriptions at the pyramid temple of Userkaf show Khaemwaset with offering bearers, and at the pyramid temple of Sahure Khaemwaset offers a statue of the goddess Bast.”
https://ancientegypt.fandom.com/wiki/Khaemwaset_A#Restoration_projects

“Khaemwaset is attested at the sun temple of Niuserre” (Almansa-Villatoro et al., 2022, mentioning Gomaà, 1973).

“Distinctive markers of Khaemwaset’s activities are the inscriptions in the names of he and his father added to several standing monuments in the Memphite necropolis and at other sites. These texts are known both from surviving examples but may in some cases be attested indirectly from later accounts of the appearance of monuments. The Unas pyramid inscription was found on its south side [41], and is now restored in that position.” (Price, 2022, mentioning Drioton and Lauer, 1937).

“It is the best preserved of such texts and is typical in formulation, being framed by a royal command: ‘His Majesty decreed an announcement; It is the High Priest (of Ptah), the Sem-priest, King’s Son Khaemwaset, who has perpetuated the name of King [Unas]. Now his name was not found on the face of his pyramid. Very greatly did the Sem-priest, King’s Son Khaemwaset, desire to restore the monuments of the Kings of Upper and Lower Egypt, because of what they had done, the strength of which was falling into decay. He set forth a decree for its sacred offerings,... its water ... [endowed] with a grant of land, together with its personnel...’. (writer’s translation)” (Price, 2022).

“Other such inscriptions appear in different positions on individual monuments: on the north side of the mastaba of Shepseskaf [1] (p. 77, no. 12); the south side of the Step Pyramid [1] (p. 77, no. 8); the east side of the pyramid of Userkaf [1] (p. 77, no. 9); the south side of the sun temple of Niuserre at Abu Ghurab [1] (p. 76, no. 4); an unknown location on the pyramid of Sahure at Abusir [41] (pp. 205–207); and on the south side of the pyramid of Pepi I at Saqqara [42].” (Price, 2022, referring to [1] Gomaà, [41] Drioton and Lauer, 1937, and [42] Leclant, 1993).

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